

The Efficiency of Marketing Channels of Coffee To you Café Of Rajamangala University of Technology Isan

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ABSTRACT: This research aim to study of the effectiveness of offline marketing channels and online marketing channels. To compare the effectiveness of marketing channels in order to be able to meet the needs of the target customer according to what the customer wants. By offline marketing channels has used a marketing channel (7P) as a strategy to test its performance. As for online marketing channels has led the way of entertainment, interaction, popularity and specificity. According to the research results, it was found that online marketing channels and online marketing channels it is effective at a high level, and online marketing channels outperforming offline marketing channels.

KEYWORDS –Efficiency, Marketing Chanel, Rajamangala University of Technology

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, we can see that most consumers popular to shop online. Because they focus on speed, ease, convenience, and no need to get tired of traveling. However, we may forget that offline channels have always been a selling strength. Where we saw the real product or getting a product presentation from the seller more clearly than looking through a mobile screen. Many businesses over the past year have devoted their more marketing budgets to online. Until making the offline storefront less important although it may have been a strong channel before.[1] Whether it is a shop restaurant or coffee shop can be seen from businesses and shops.

Coffee Shop Cafe To You of Rajamangala University of Technology Isan is a coffee shop of the tourism and hotel department at Rajamangala University of Technology Isan. The shop has developed a coffee shop, drinking menu to meet the needs of customers. And also, to increase sales for the coffee shop and to focus on creating a seating area for the customers who come to use the service has a relaxed and social atmosphere or, sometimes used as a teacher or student office by means of a service channel, whether it is a storefront or an order.

To increase efficiency in marketing channels online marketing alone may not be enough, so many shops are looking for other ways to join them.[2] To make the shop more famous decorating the storefront to have gimmicks to attract customers to take photos and share them on social media. Online marketing becoming increasingly influential, but traditional offline media marketing is still a necessity, as choosing just one type of market can't get the shop to reach the entire target customers.

From the above, the researcher wants to study the distribution channel efficiency of Coffee To Youcafé of Rajamangala University of Technology Isan both offline and online and to compare the distribution channel efficiency of both coffee shops. To develop sales channels and as a guideline for increasing sales for coffee shops and improve updates to be able to develop further sales for better in the future.

II. OBJECTIVES/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research paper examines the effectiveness of offline marketing channels and online marketing channels.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework

III. METHODOLOGY

This study is quantitative research that provides broad, empirical data that can be applied to all areas to check with the theoretical framework set forth by the researcher based on the principles, concepts and theories to get the findings on key issues. The researcher collected data using a questionnaire with customer of Coffee To You café in 2020. We determine sample sizes that are 348 by using formula for non-population. The tools of research by questionnaire, created a questionnaire based on the operational definition that the developer of the instrumentation and has been improved to fit the research. A questionnaire have been developed to the experts to examine the content validity of the question from the study of related theoretical and literary concepts. After the questionnaire matched with the characteristics of the research objectives to be measured, content validity and suitability and cover the content that the researcher wants to study. The reliability of the questionnaire was tested by 30 participants. This is not a research sample. The reliability of the questionnaire was 0.899 with the α value of 0.70 and above was considered to be the confidence question [3]

Data analysis: the researcher took the data from the distribution of questionnaires. All of them were analyzed and calculated by means of descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage and standard deviation. It presents information in the form of lectures and performance comparisons, offline marketing channels and online marketing channels. The testing of the difference between the mean of two samples was analyzed by statistical analysis-test analysis of variance: ANOVA and multiple regression analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings indicates the researcher divided the topic into two parts, with the details as follows.

1. Average data of variables; Offline, Online and Marketing Channels Efficiency.

Table 1 Average data of Offline Marketing Channels

Offline Marketing Channels	\bar{X}	S.D.	Mean
1. Product	4.12	0.48	High
2. Price	4.11	0.48	High
3. Place	3.80	0.62	High
4. Promotion	3.36	1.19	Medium
5. People	4.09	0.54	High
6. Process	4.29	0.57	High

7. Physical Evidence	4.12	0.53	High
Total	3.98	0.47	High

From the table 1 of the efficacy of offline marketing channels, the overall result was at a high level (\bar{x} = 3.98, SD = 0.47) found that the users of the service had a high level of physical opinion (\bar{x} = 4.28, SD = 0.57), followed by the process at a high level (\bar{x} = 4.12, SD = 0.53), followed by the product and the price high level (\bar{x} = 4.11, SD = 0.48), etc. Consistent with the study of Nathaphong Chotipreecharat. [4] Study service marketing mix factors affecting consumers' decision to choose Japanese restaurants in Nimmanhaemin Road, Mueang Chiang Mai District, found that consumers care about to a large extent in the field of freshness of food and beverages. Variety of food and drink items food and beverage prices are reasonable for the quality food and drink prices are not. The restaurant changes frequently and the restaurant has a fixed opening-closing time, enough seats for customers. [4]

Table 2 Average data of Online Marketing Channels

Online Marketing Channels	\bar{X}	S.D.	Mean
1. Entertainment	4.22	0.82	High
2. Interaction	4.16	0.57	High
3. Popularity	4.08	0.73	High
4. Specificity	4.12	0.73	High
Total	4.15	0.56	High

From the table 2 of the effectiveness of online marketing channels, the overall study was at a high level (\bar{x} = 4.15, SD = 0.56). It was found that the users of the service had a high level of entertainment opinions (\bar{x} = 4.22, SD = 0.82), followed by the interaction at the high level (\bar{x} = 4.15, SD = 0.57), followed by the specific aspect at a high level (\bar{x} = 4.11, SD = 0.73) and the popularity was at a high level (\bar{x} = 4.08, SD = 0.73), respectively. Consistent with research of Kan Thi Pempian [5] to study appropriate marketing strategies for small coffee shops. In the area of higher education institutions in Chiang Mai. [4]

Research results marketing channel efficiency of Coffee for You of Rajamangala University of Technology Isan from Table 3.

Table 3 Average data of Marketing Channels Efficiency

Marketing Channels Efficiency	\bar{X}	S.D.	Mean
1 metI	4.20	0.87	High
2 metI	4.10	0.94	High
Item 3	4.05	0.94	High
Total	4.11	0.83	High

From the table 3 of the effectiveness of marketing channels, the overall study was at a high level (\bar{x} = 4.11, SD = 0.83). It was found that the users of the service had a high level of item 1 (\bar{x} = 4.20, SD = 0.87), followed by item 2 at the high level (\bar{x} = 4.10, SD = 0.94) and item 3 was at a high level (\bar{x} = 4.05, SD = 0.94), respectively.

Table 4 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.830 ^a	.897	.393	.844	.399

a. Predictors: (Constant), Offline Marketing Channels, Online Marketing Channels

b. Dependent Variable: Marketing Channels Efficiency

From the table the online marketing channels and offline marketing channels have effective 0.897 or 89.7%. It is 0.103 or 10.3% effective of other factors.

Table 5 Compare Marketing Channels Efficiency

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.751	.360		3.253	.000

Offline Marketing Channels	.601	.074	.035	2.827	.000
OnlineMarketing Channels	.941	.063	.635	14.949	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Word of Mouth

From the table 5 compare marketing channels efficiency of offline marketing channels and online marketing channels effective. It is found that the effective as online marketing channels outperform offline marketing channels.

V. CONCLUSION

From the study on the efficiency of marketing channels for coffee for you of Rajamangala University of Technology Isan. By comparing the effectiveness of offline marketing channels (7P marketing strategy) and online marketing channels, including entertainment channels. In terms of the specific popularity relationship, it was found that today the internet has influenced consumer behavior in making purchasing decisions. It's easy and convenient. Consumers can access information quickly. Including making decisions on how to buy products via the Internet As a result, organizations need to adjust their strategies to adapt to changing consumer behavior. And from the results of the analysis of the effectiveness of online marketing communications using word-of-mouth, it was able to build a good relationship with the target audience, which had a statistically significant effect on purchasing intent at 0.05 level.

References:

- [1] Tongsongyod, S. & Kai-nunna, P. (2018). Marketing Channel Development for Salt Product of Bana District, Pattani Province. *Journal of Business, Economics and Communications*, 13(1).
- [2] Millet, J. D. (1954). *Management in the Public Service*. New York: McGraw Hill Book Company.
- [3] Kattiya, S & Suvajittanon, W. (2012). *Research and Statistic Models*, Bangkok : Prayoonwong Printing Co. LTD.
- [4] Chotipreecharat, N. (2009). *Service Marketing Mix Factors Affecting the Decision of Consumers in Selecting Japanese Restaurants in Nimmanhaemin Road, Mueang Chiang Mai District*. Chiang Mai: Independent Study Master of Business Administration Graduate School Mahawatiyalaya Chiang Mai, 2009.
- [5] Permphan, K. T. (2010). *To Study Appropriate Marketing Strategies for Small Coffee Shops. In the Area of Higher Education Institutions, Chiang Mai Province*. (Independent research, Master of Business Administration Chiang Mai University).